

A Study On Challenges Of Women Entrepreneurs In India (A Case Study of Women Entrepreneurs of Jodhpur city of Rajasthan)

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Abstract

“Women who innovate initiate or adopt business actively are called women entrepreneurs.”

-J.Schumpeter “Women entrepreneurship is based on women participation in equity and employment of a business enterprise.” -Ruhani J. Alice Women entrepreneur means that section of the female population who takes up industrial activities like manufacturing, assembling, job works, repairs/serving and other businesses. Indian women is changing and they are fast emerging as potential entrepreneurs. They are playing a very important role in business, trade or industry. This paper discusses the factors behind entry of females in entrepreneurship. It also discusses the Government schemes to encourage women entrepreneurship. It also throws light on the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs and also provides suggestions to increase women entrepreneurship and to strengthen women entrepreneurship. The research is based on primary data collected from women entrepreneurs of Jodhpur city of Rajasthan. 100 female entrepreneurs have been selected for survey.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurship, Government Schemes, Challenges, Prospects.

INTRODUCTION

An entrepreneur is an economic agent who takes risks with the expectation of earning more and more profits. Entrepreneur is an innovator, decision maker and risk taker. Women entrepreneurs are those who do forecasting, planning, organizing, directing and manage their enterprise. Initiating and operating a business enterprise that leads to economic empowerment and improves the living standard of women in the society can be termed as women entrepreneurship. According to Government of India, women entrepreneur is the one who assumes dominant financial control (minimum financial interest of 51%) of the capital in an enterprise. After the liberalization and globalization female entrepreneurship is increasing worldwide. Women entrepreneurs are gaining importance both in developed and developing countries. Women entrepreneurship contributes in creating employment opportunities, removal of poverty and increase per capital income of any country. Entrepreneurship play an important role in the development of any country. India is not performing well in case of development of female entrepreneurship. Status of higher education in females in India is lower than most countries in the world. The number of female entrepreneurs who are owners of large scale industries is limited. Even in Small scale industries female entrepreneurs are not performing well. As per the third all India census of

small scale industries only 10.11% of the micro and small enterprises were owned by women and only 9.46% of them are managed by women. According to MasterCard Index of women entrepreneurs only 7% female entrepreneurs are in India. According to report by the World Economic Forum 2021 there is a gender gap of 72% in India's labour market. Only 20% of the business in the country are owned by women as per the Google Brain report. But the number of female entrepreneurs is increasing gradually. They are facing lots of obstacles like lack of capital. Lack of awareness of Government schemes and plans, lack of support from family members etc. In past the activities of females were limited to 3P's, Pickle, powder and papad. But nowadays with the spread of education females started shifting from 3P's to modern 3 E's i.e. Energy, Electronics and Engineering.

Review of Literature

Singh, 2008, identifies the causes behind women taking up entrepreneurship. He explained the nature of their businesses in Indian context and also problems faced by them. He found that the problems of women entrepreneurship are mainly lack of exposure, no interaction with successful entrepreneurs, social pressure ,family responsibility, gender discrimination, missing network and problems is arranging adequate capital . He has given suggestions like promoting micro enterprises, promoting

self help groups and Ngo's for providing finance.

Tambunan, (2009), made a study on women entrepreneurs working in Asian developing countries. This study found that in Asian developing countries Small and medium enterprises are gaining o importance more than 95% of all firms in all sectors on average per country. The study also concluded that representation of women entrepreneurs in this region is relatively low due to factors like lack of literacy, lack of finance and social or religious constraints. However, the study revealed that most of the women entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises are from the category of forced entrepreneurs seeking for better family incomes.

Centindamar et al (2012) did his study on the relative importance of the three types of capital for business: human, family, and financial, play a major in becoming entrepreneurs regardless of sex. He also found that the impact of human capital on the probability of becoming an entrepreneur is greater for women than for men. The data also revealed in large family's female entrepreneurship gets the facility of capital. Gender differences were not observed with respect to the impact of financial capital Boz et al. (2016) discovered that women who care most about the family have negative behaviors at work, consequently, the balance between family and work is more difficult for women entrepreneurs, which represents a fundamental obstacle to the growth of their businesses. Rembulan et al. (2016) has compared women entrepreneurs and women employees and found that, women entrepreneurs, compared to women who work as employees, have very low levels of conflict regarding time management and family care. Malik and Rao (2018) did their study on 135 women entrepreneurs in Chandigarh to find out the purposes behind beginning business, reasons for their success in business and quality credited to their success. It was found that women were ready to face the challenges related with setting up of business. Chips, badiya, pickles were the items of past times, presently with new and imaginative business, women entrepreneurs were quick turning into a power to figure with in the business world. Women were not working for arranging income but also for fulfilling their dreams and to prove herself into society.

Women education was adding, all things considered, to the social transformation.

Objectives of the study

To study the factors behind entry of women in entrepreneurship

To study the Government schemes to encourage women entrepreneurship

To study the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs

To give suggestions and draw conclusions

Research Methodology

The research is based on primary data collected from women entrepreneurs of Jodhpur city of Rajasthan. 100 female entrepreneurs have been selected for survey. They were given questionnaire to fill. Interviews were also taken for research purposes. After studying the questionnaire and on the basis of interviews taken results were drawn. The research is also based on secondary data taken from journals, annual reports, Government documents, newspapers and websites.

Factors behind entry of Women in Entrepreneurship:

Push Factors:

Death of Father, husband or son

Economic problem of the family

Sudden fall in family income

Pull Factors:

Desire to become economically independent.

To gain recognition, importance and social status.

To utilize their spare time or education

Women's desire to use their skills or talent,

1. Family culture and traditions influence entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneur will remain entrepreneur if its family tradition is so or if she belongs to a pioneer entrepreneur.

2. The society the state and the area to which she belongs also influence the entrepreneurship. If she is a Marathi or Marwari belonging to their respective state, will become entrepreneurs.

3. The caste system also influences as a women who is Mahajan may start a business at an early stage as in their caste or communities it is a trend. Government aids and policies – Government can never increase entrepreneurship, it always helps an entrepreneur. A capable person only can become entrepreneur even if she gets aids or adopts policies to start a venture.

4. Government can help poor class people with reservations.

5. Capabilities to withstand the competition with males requires guts and dare to become an entrepreneur. Females require same capabilities as that of males. They get benefit of being females only when the service has to be rendered to women only like in hospitals etc. Capabilities influence the entrepreneurship but efficiency is also required as if the person has capability to become an entrepreneur but if she is not efficient to run the venture she cannot become a better entrepreneurship.

Schemes for Female Entrepreneurs by Government of India

There have been development of Women entrepreneurs in India from last many decades and have been playing a very important role in business or industry.. Several policies and programmes have been formulated by the Government of India to develop women entrepreneurs in India. They have been briefly described below:

- 1) The Seventh Five Year Plan (1985-90) provided a special chapter on Integration of Woman in Development. In this article, it had made the following suggestions for the development of a woman viz
 - i) To treat women as specific target group in all development programs
 - ii) To properly diversify vocational training facilities for women to suit their varied needs and skills.
 - iii) To encourage appropriate technologies, equipment's and practice for reducing their drudgery and increase their productivity.
 - iv) To provide marketing assistance at the State level.
 - v) To increase women's participation in decision-making.
- 2) In 1981, the First National Conference of Women Entrepreneurs was held at New Delhi and it urged the Government to give priority to women in the allotment of lands, sheds, sanction of power, industrial licensing etc. It also recommended for simplifying loan procedures, counseling services, centralised marketing agency and special training programmes for women entrepreneurs.
- 3) In 1989, Second International Conference of Women Entrepreneurs organised by the National Alliance of Young Entrepreneurs (NAYE) was held in New Delhi under the aegis of the World Assembly of Small and Medium Enterprises (WASME). It adopted a declaration containing the following important features:

- i) All the national governments of the countries should (a) promote involvement of women in economic and social programmes, (b) provide necessary infrastructural facilities, training and marketing facilities, (c) enact legislation to remove constraints in their way and (d) arrange for transfer of relevant technology and financial assistance.

- ii) The international agencies such as UNCTAD, UNDP, ILO and the national governments should adopt appropriate measures for encouraging free flow of products manufactured by women entrepreneurs and should provide fiscal and expert assistance to the governments and other agencies engaged in the promotion of women entrepreneurship.

- iii) The products manufactured by women entrepreneurs should be widely displayed in national and international trade fairs.

- iv) The education ministries of the various countries and the UNESCO should provide necessary literature, books, and publications for the benefit of women entrepreneurs.

- 4) The 1991 Industrial Policy of the Government of India also stressed the need for conducting special entrepreneurship programmes for women. It also suggested for conducting product and process-oriented courses for women to enable them to start small scale industrial enterprises. It further adds that the objective of such courses should be to give representation to women in the field of small industry development in order to lift their status in the economic and social fields.

- 5) During the Eighth Five year Plan (1992-97), the following special programmes were introduced to increase employment and income generating activities for women –

- i) In agriculture, during 1993, a programme for training women farmers was launched.

- ii) Women Co-operatives – A programme for formation of women co-operatives was launched for helping woman engaged in agro-based industries.

- iii) Khadi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC) took measures to provide more and more employment opportunities for women.

- iv) Several Development Programmes were launched specially for women e.g. Prime Minister's Rozgar Yojana (MPRY), Entrepreneurial Development Programme (EDPs), Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP), Jawaharlal Rozgar

Yojana (JRY), Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas etc.

6) During the Ninth Five Year Plan (1997-2002), special strategy was adopted by the Central and State Governments to help the women entrepreneurs as follows –

i) Women Component Plan to provide not less than 30 percent of funds for all women related schemes.

ii) Women Development Corporation (WDCs) to provide forward and backward linkages of credit and marketing facilities to women entrepreneurs of small and tiny sectors.

iii) Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD) introduced in 1998 aims at economic empowerment of women in rural, urban and semi-urban areas. It also aims at developing their entrepreneurial skills, eliminating constraints faced by them, and strengthening their trade support net-works. It operates through SIDBI.

iv) Prime Minister Rozgar Yojana (PMRY) introduced in the VIII plan, and in April, 1999 amended to modify eligibility criteria and some other parameters such as relaxing the age of women.

v) Swarna Jayanthi Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY) and Swarnajayanthi Shahari Rozgar Yojana (SJSRY) provide reservation for women, encourage group activities among them and help them in several ways.

vi) Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) has sponsored several schemes with the objective of providing training and extension support services to women entrepreneurs through a comprehensive package designed according to their skills, socio-economic status and to extend liberal financial help to enable them to set industrial units in small scale sector. These schemes include

a) Women Entrepreneurial Development Programmes (WEDPs)

b) Marketing Development Fund for Women Entrepreneurs (MDFWE)

c) Mahila Udyam Nidhi (MUN)

d) Mahila Vikas Nidhi (MVN)

e) Micro Credit Scheme (MCS)

vii) Industrial Estate for Women Entrepreneurs – There has been an insistent demand for setting up industrial estates particularly for women entrepreneurs. The Andhra Pradesh State Government has supported for setting up industrial estates

exclusively for women in three districts. These industrial estates are meant for

(a) setting up electronics, garments, food processing, printing, bio-technology, handmade paper, small engineering units, accessories etc.

(b) export-oriented units like mushroom processing, computer hardware and software etc, and

(c) Software Technology Park for women within the industrial estate.

7) Consortium of Women Entrepreneurs of India (CWEI) – It is a common platform to help the women entrepreneurs in finding innovative techniques of production, marketing and finance in the context of the opening up of the economy and the need for upgradation of technology. It consists of (a) NGOs, (b) Voluntary Organisations, (c) Self-help Groups, (d) Institutions and (e) Individual Enterprises from urban and rural areas.

8) Mahila Vikas Nidhi – Under this scheme, a cumulative help of Rs. 80.4 million has been sanctioned during the period of 1999-2001 to 155 NGOs/Agencies benefitting around 21,350 women entrepreneurs, for providing training and employment opportunities to women in rural areas. The training centres set up by NGOs mostly relate to activities such as sericulture, spinning, weaving, block printing, handicrafts, handloom products etc.

9) Micro Credit Scheme – This scheme of Rs. 810.50 million has been sanctioned by SIDBI i.e. Small Industries Development Bank of India to 169 MFIs benefitting over 4,42,000 poor women since the inception of this scheme.

10) Prime Minister's Rozgar Yojana – Under this scheme, Women-oriented schemes of IDBI, SFCs (State Finance Corporations, KVIC etc. have been introduced for the benefit of women entrepreneurs by granting loans.

11) Rastriya Mahila Kosh – This was set up in 1993 for providing micro credit poor women who have no access to financial institutions at reasonable or fair rates of interest.

12) Training Programmes – Various training programmes have been started by the Government of India exclusively meant for women for self-employment. The training programmes include Support for Training and Employment Programme of Women (STEP), Development of Women and

Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA) and setting up of Trainingcum-Employment-cum-Production Units (NORAD).

13) District Industries Centers (DICs) – These centres have arranged various lectures, seminars etc. in girls colleges and technical institutions.

14) University Grants Commission (UGC) – The UGC has introduced the subject of entrepreneurship as a compulsory subject in the curriculum in the colleges of all universities in India. Thus, various measures have been implemented by the Central Government and State Governments and other associations and organizations for the development of women.

Challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in India

1. Economic Problem

A female entrepreneur faces problems in arranging funds to start her business because Indian women do not have property or assets in their name. They also face problem while applying for loans due to lack of collateral.

2. Social Problem

It is found that when women start an entrepreneurial venture they find no support of family and friends. There is no one to guide them. They had to find their way themselves. Even family responsibilities are not shared by their family members. So it becomes very difficult for a woman to look after dual responsibilities.

3. Lack of education

According to UNESCO's education report, about 68% of the illiterate population of India are females. As most of the female entrepreneurs are less educated they find problems in managing the business, decision

Findings and observations

The result of study done on female entrepreneurs is shown in the form of tables.

Table 1

1. Types of Business chosen by female entrepreneurs

1	Manufacturing	24
2	Trading	55
3	Agro-based Industries	21
Total		100

Data: Field survey

It is found that 55% of the female entrepreneurs were indulged in trading activities. The numbers of Female

making, financial management, maintaining accounts etc. Due to this businesses run by female entrepreneurs do not make more profits and sometimes it becomes difficult to survive.

4. Problem of Gender Biasness

Entrepreneurship is mostly dominated by males. Presently, the scenario is changing but there is still a long way to go. According to a report, the percentage of female start-up founders in India is only 11%. India has the third largest start-up base in the entire world but the number of female entrepreneurs is less.

5. Problem of dual responsibility

For females family is first priority. They have an important responsibility of handling a household and taking care of their children. It requires long hours to own and run a business and thus for women work-life balance can become a problem.

6. Problem of limited mobility

In India females mostly depend on males to move from one place to another. They fear while travelling alone. To run a business successfully an entrepreneur has to move from one place to another frequently. The percentages of females are less who move independently without any fear from one place to another. That is why females are not becoming successful entrepreneurs.

7. Problem of lack of Motivation

In India the traditional and orthodox families do not support females to start any venture. If they start on their own, they lack motivation. And in the event of failures they do not get any support. Not all women are fortunate to have cooperative and understanding family members.

entrepreneurs were less in Agro-based industries.

Table 2

2. Factors behind Setting up business by female entrepreneurs

1	For fulfilling financial requirements of family	30
2	To improve the social status	05
3	To make use of skills	20
4	To utilize spare time	10
5	To become financially independent	15
6	To own a land/house	20
Total		100

Data: Field survey

Table two shows that 30% of the females are doing their own business for fulfilling requirements of family. Only 5% of the

females are doing their on business for improving their social status.

Table 3

Social problems of Female Entrepreneurs

1	Lack of literacy	30
2	No family support	24
3	Dual responsibilities	39
4	Gender difference	07
Total		100

Data: Field survey

Table 3 shows that about 39% of female entrepreneurs has dual responsibility of looking after family members and looking after the business. They face problems because to manage a business requires long hours. They cannot devote long hours to business because family is their first priority and hence they could not become successful

entrepreneurs. About 30% of female entrepreneurs could not grow because they lack formal and non-formal education. About 24% of the female entrepreneurs have no family support. And 7% of the female entrepreneurs were suffering from male hostility.

Table 4

Problems during managing the business

1	Arrangement of Resources	40
2	Arrangement of Capital	30
3	Lack of Conveyance facility	10
4	Collection of Payment	20
Total		100

Source: Field survey

The table shows that about 40% of female entrepreneurs' faces problem regarding arrangement of resources. About 30% of females faces financial problem.

Suggestions for Increasing Women Entrepreneurs

As women entrepreneurs face economic, social, cultural and technical problems they are less in India than any other developed countries. Venture means a small enterprise and it will become an enterprise which deals with comparatively large scale units and will become an entrepreneur in the end. There is a need of entrepreneurs and it can be gapped to some extent if women entrepreneurs also increase in number. Several women conferences have concluded to encourage women entrepreneurship:

1. PCPNDT Act should be implemented strictly and female fetus should not be aborted .
2. Girls should be imparted compulsory and free education and be given equal rights in nutrition, education, training and skill building activities and in employment.
3. There should be no discrimination between males and females in employment and should be paid equally for work done.
4. Women should be given right in properties and awareness programmes should be conducted regarding Right to Property Act 2005. .
5. Interest free loans should be provided to female entrepreneurs or at lower rates by banks and Private agencies after legal formalities and search for authenticity.

6. Family members instead of giving dowry at the time of marriage should provide money at the time of starting business and always encourage and assist the female entrepreneurs to grow.

7. Females should be given help with franchise and starting ventures in lines suited for female clients.

9. Government should start awareness programmes for the women entrepreneurs. Government has started many programs but they should be implemented properly..

Suggestions to strengthen Women Entrepreneurship

To strengthen women's entrepreneurship, all the present development programmes and policies should be planned properly and implemented effectively in order to attain self sufficiency and self-reliance. "Women constitute half of the world's population, accomplish about two thirds of its work hours receive one-tenth (1/10) of the world's income." — Union Commission on status of Women The following measures can strengthen self-employment, which will generate additional income leading to economic independence of women:

1. Training programmes should be organized for developing entrepreneurship abilities among women entrepreneurs.

2. There should representation of women experts in programmes related to development of women.

3. Formal and non-formal education regarding entrepreneurship be provided to females so that they can make effective planning at the micro level

4. Awareness programmes should be organized regarding technical and financial assistance available to women entrepreneurs.

5. A separate department should be established by the Government at the central, state and district levels to look after women's entrepreneurship and their problems.

6. Supervisory bodies should be established to monitor the implementation of constitutional provisions related to women.

8. Women entrepreneurs should be encouraged by providing various incentives and concessions and exemption in tax.

9. In order to find out new opportunities in the field of women entrepreneurship the Government should encourage research and development programmes.

10. The concept of co-operative should be developed by Government specially for the financial assistance and marketing purposes.

Conclusion

In order to make a developing country into a developed country women entrepreneurship is must. In India the number of female entrepreneurs is limited. Female population is 50% of the total population of the country yet economic participation of women is limited. It is because a female faces numerous challenges in the course of their entrepreneurial career. There is need of comprehensive action plan to counter these challenges. Initiative, independence, self-confidence, positive thinking are among the qualities that should be nurtured to make a positive impact on the business. Suggestions have been to increase the number of women entrepreneurs and to strengthen women entrepreneurship. Many Government schemes have been launched to motivate and support women entrepreneurship. Impact assessment of existing policies and schemes is the need of the hour.

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